

Phenylpropionic Acids. Part X.¹ Addition of Phenyl Azide and Certain Nucleophilic Reagents to Acetylenic Esters and Ketones

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Manuscript received 9 March 1973; accepted 27 June 1973

Phenyl Azide condensed with ethyl arylpropiolates to give a mixture of 5-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (predominant) and 4-aryl-5-ethoxycarbonyl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles. The acid azides derived from the former isomers were converted into the corresponding ureides by refluxing in benzene. Similarly aryl phenyl acetylenes gave a mixture of 4-aryl-1,5-diphenyl- and 5-aryl-1,4-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazoles. Hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine condensed with aryl phenyl acetylenes to give 3(5)-aryl-5(3)-phenyl-pyrazoles and 3-aryl-1,5-diphenylpyrazoles, respectively.

It has been reported² that ethyl phenylpropiolate condensed with phenyl azide to give 1,5-diphenyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-1,2,3-triazole (1a). However, when the reaction was repeated with the same ester and with ethyl *p*-chlorophenyl- and *p*-tolyl-propiolates a mixture of 5-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (major) (1a, 2 and 3) and 4-aryl-5-ethoxycarbonyl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (minor) (5, 6 and 7) was obtained, respectively. Ethyl *p*-anisylpropiolate, however, gave only the 5-aryl-isomer (4). (cf. Scheme I)

The u.v. spectra (Table 1) show that (5), (6) and (7) absorb at a longer wavelength than (1), (2) and (3), respectively, which is attributed to steric interaction between the two aryl groups.

The structure of (1a) was rigidly established by its conversion by hydrolysis into 1,5-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid³ (1b). Decarboxylation of (1b) gave (8); which was identical with an authentic specimen.⁴ (cf. Scheme I)

Huisgen⁵ has shown that the addition of a 1,3-dipole to a dipolarophile occurs by a concerted mechanism in which the two new σ -bonds are formed simultaneously although not necessarily at equal rates. The formation of a mixture of the two isomeric triazoles could be understood, since phenyl azide is a resonance hybrid of two contributing structures (A) and (B); with (A) as the major contributor,⁶ (Scheme I)

The low yield of the 4-aryl-1-phenyl-isomers (5, 6 and 7) (Table 1) is in good agreement with the smaller contribution of (B) to the resonance hybrid of phenyl azide.

Hydrazine hydrate condensed with 5-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonyl- (1a, 2-4) (cf. Scheme II) and 4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-ethoxycarbonyl- (6) -1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole (cf. Scheme I) at room temperature to give the corresponding acylhydrazides (9-13, respectively). The alternative structure (14) possible for such compounds was excluded from the n.m.r. spectrum of (9), which did not show any signal for an

TABLE I

Cpd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Found				Formula	Required				λ_{max} /nm	ϵ	ν_{C-O} /cm ⁻¹
			C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl			
(1a)	69.0	138-9*	70.0	5.1	14.7		C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	69.6	5.1	14.3		246	12500	1715 br.
(2)	61.0	136-7*	62.5	4.7	12.9	10.6	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClO	62.3	4.3	12.8	10.6	250	16240	1713 br.
(3)	65.5	120-1*	70.3	5.6	13.8		C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	70.7	5.5	13.8		250	14300	1717 br.
(4)	60.0	92-4‡	67.0	5.8	13.4		C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	66.9	5.3	13.0		258-262	14750	1715
(5)	3.6	87-8‡	70.1	5.0	14.9		C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	69.6	5.1	14.3		272	11230	1725
(6)	25.9	71‡	62.7	4.1	13.0	10.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClO	62.3	4.3	12.8	10.8	274	14200	1725
(7)	1.6	111@	70.8	5.3	14.0		C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	70.7	5.5	13.8		276	16540	1725

* From light petroleum (b.p. 100-120°); ‡ From light petroleum (b.p. 80°-100°); @From light petroleum (b.p. 60°-80°), mixed m.p. with (3) 94°.

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Scheme I

Scheme II

aliphatic proton. However, the structure assigned to these hydrazides was substantiated by converting (9-11) into the corresponding acyl azides (15-17) on being treated with nitrous acid. (cf Scheme II)

The structure of the acyl azides (15-17) was established from their i.r. spectra (see experimental). Thermolysis of the acyl azides (15) and (16), even by refluxing in dry benzene, gave the corresponding

TABLE 2

Cpd.	M.p. (°C)	Found				Formula	Required				λ_{maz} / nm	ϵ	$\nu_{C=O}$ / cm ⁻¹	ν_{NH} / cm ⁻¹
		C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl				
(9)	166-7	64.6	4.9	24.3		C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O	64.5	4.7	25.1		242-6	3100	1600	—
(10)	195-6	57.8	4.1	22.4	11.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₅ ClO	57.4	3.8	22.2	11.3	251	17200	1652	—
(11)	202-4	65.6	5.5	23.7		C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₅ O	65.5	5.1	23.9		239	24740	1660	—
(12)	177-9	62.1	5.0	22.0		C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂	62.1	4.8	22.65				1660	—
(13)	187-9	57.2	3.8	22.8	11.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₅ ClO	57.4	3.8	22.2	11.3	249	20620	1660	—
(20)	240	70.1	4.6	22.4		C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₆ O	69.9	4.4	22.5		238-244	22000	1718	—
(21)	252	61.1	3.7	20.2	12.6	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ Cl ₂ O	61.5	3.5	19.8	12.5	248	21670	1700	—
(22)	124* ⁹	70.6	5.2	24.1		C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄	71.1	5.2	23.7		288	7980	—	3440
														3290
														3180
(23)	161-2@	62.5	4.1	20.6	13.1	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ Cl	62.1	4.1	20.7	13.1	204	12790	—	3420
														3285
														3170

* From light petroleum (b.p. 100°-120°). @ From benzene.

TABLE 3

Cpd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Found				Formula	Required				λ_{maz} / nm	$\nu_{C=O}$ / cm ⁻¹	
			C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl			
(27)	79.6	164-6 ¹⁰	77.9	4.9	13.4		C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₃ O	77.5	4.65	12.9		259.0	21650	1657
(28)	65.5	168-70	70.5	3.9	11.4	9.7	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClO	70.1	3.9	11.7	9.9	268.0	23490	1650
(29)	50.0	196	74.9	4.8	11.75		C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	74.4	4.8	11.8		298.0	21380	1643
												223.0	20050	
(30)	20.7	165-7@*	70.3	3.8	11.9	10.3	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClO	70.1	3.9	11.7	9.9	266.0	19170	1660
(31)	30.0	158-60*	74.4	4.7	11.8		C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	74.4	4.8	11.8		302.5	19650	1660
												234.0	25940	

* From ethanol.

@ Mixed m.p. with (28) 141°-3°.

ureides (20) and (21). Their formation seems to involve first a Curtius rearrangement to give the isocyanates (18) and (19), which then reacted with the amines (22) and (23), respectively. Formation of these amines cannot be explained unless partial hydrolysis of the corresponding isocyanates occurs during the reaction by traces of humidity.

The structure of the ureides (20) and (21) was inferred from the following: (a) i.r. spectra which show both ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} , and (b) the formation of 4-amino-5-aryl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (22) and (23), when (20) and (21), respectively, were hydrolysed with 50% sulphuric acid. These amines undergo the usual diazotisation and coupling reactions.

Similarly, phenyl azide condensed with benzoyl-phenylacetylene (24) to give 4-benzoyl-1,5-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazole (27) and with (25) and (26) to give a mixture of 4-royl-1,5-diphenyl- (28 and 29) and 5-royl-1,4-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (30 and 31), respectively. (cf. Scheme I)

The u.v. spectra of the isomers (Table 3) are identical and gave no indication to differentiate between them.

The structure of 4-royl-1,5-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (28) and (29) was rigidly established by their identity

with authentic specimens, prepared by interaction of the acid chloride (32) with chlorobenzene and anisole, respectively, in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. (cf. Scheme I)

Aroylphenylacetylenes (24-26) condensed with hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine to give 3(5)-aryl-5(3)-phenyl-pyrazoles (33a, 34a and 35a) and 3-aryl-1,5-diphenylpyrazoles (33b, 34b and 35b), respectively. (cf. Scheme I)

The structure of (33a) was established by its identity with an authentic specimen.⁷ Compounds (34a) and (35a) have analogous u.v. spectra to that of (33a) (Table 4).

The structure of (33b) was established by its identity with an authentic specimen.⁷ Compounds (34b) and (35b) have analogous u.v. spectra to that of (33b) (Table 4)

Experimental

I.r. spectra (KBr discs) were measured on a Unicam SP 1200 Spectrophotometer, and u.v. spectra (in ethanol) on a Perkin-Elmer Spectracord Model 4000 A.

5 (or 4)-Aryl-4 (or 5)-ethoxycarbonyl-1,2,3-triazoles: A solution of ethyl arylpropiolate (0.02 mol) and

TABLE 4

Cpd.	M.p. (°C)	Found				Formula	Required				$\lambda_{max}/$ nm	ϵ	ν_{NH}/cm^{-1}
		C	H	N	Cl		C	H	N	Cl			
(33a)	199-200@ ⁷	81.8	5.6	13.3		C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂	81.8	5.5	12.7		253.5	33250	3280-2500
(34a)	214-5@	70.7	4.6	11.4	14.4	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl	70.7	4.3	11.0	13.9	258.0	39220	3280-2500
(35a)	168@ ¹¹	77.2	5.6	12.0		C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	76.8	5.6	11.2		260.0	42075	3280-2500
(33b)	137-9*	85.4	5.2	9.6		C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	85.1	5.4	9.45		253.0	30950	—
(34b)	115-7*	76.2	4.4	8.3	11.1	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	76.2	4.5	8.5	10.7	255.5	36165	—
(35b)	140@ ¹¹	81.1	5.7	8.7		C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	80.9	5.5	8.6		260.0	40750	—

* From methanol.

@ From ethanol.

phenyl azide (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (20 ml) was refluxed for 24 hr. The solvent was steam distilled and the residue was crystallised from a suitable solvent. 5-Aryl-1-phenyl isomer crystallised out leaving the 4-aryl-1-phenyl-isomer in the mother liquors (Table 1).

1,5-Diphenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic Acid (1b): The ester (2.9 g) was refluxed with 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (30 ml) for 2 hr, then the alcohol was removed in *vacuo* and the residue dissolved in water and extracted with ether. The product precipitated on acidification of the alkaline layer was filtered off, and crystallised from dilute methanol to give the acid (1b) (2.5 g), m.p. 183°-4° (lit.³ m.p. 184°). (Found: C, 68.1; H, 3.9; N, 16.3. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₁N₃O₂: C, 67.9; H, 4.15; N, 15.8%). $\nu_{C=O}$ at 1695 cm⁻¹ and ν_{OH} in the region 2200-3300 cm⁻¹ (br).

1,5-Diphenyl-1,2,3-triazole: The acid (1b) (0.4 g) was heated with copper-bronze (0.8 g) in boiling quinoline for 4 hr, and worked up as usual⁸ to give the product (8) (0.3 g), m.p. 113°-4° [from light petroleum (b.p. 100°-120°)], undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen.⁴

5 (or 4)-Aryl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4 (or 5)-carboxylic Acid Hydrazide (9-13): Hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) was added dropwise with occasional shaking to a solution of the ester (1 g) (1a, 2-4 and 6) in absolute ethanol (10 ml). The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 24 hr or refluxed for 5 hr, and the precipitated hydrazides (quantitative) were crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

5-Aryl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic Acid Azides (15-17): A solution of sodium nitrate (0.5 g) in the least amount of ice-cold water was added dropwise with constant stirring to an ice-cold solution of the hydrazides (9-11) (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) so that the temperature did not exceed 5°. After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 0.5 hr, and then diluted with water. The precipitated product was filtered off, and dried to give the acyl azides. Attempts to crystallise the products failed as they decompose on slight heating.

(15), (16) and (17) had m.ps. 124°, 104°-6°, and 76°, respectively. I.r. spectra show bands at 1690-1705 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{C=O}$ and at 2125-2140 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{N\equiv N}$

Thermolysis of the Acyl Azides (15) and (16): The solution of (15) and (16) (1 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 hr. The solid precipitated on cooling was filtered off and crystallised from xylene to give (20) and (21) in nearly quantitative yield.

4-Amino-5-aryl-1-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (22) and (23): The urpides (20) and (21) (0.5 g) were heated for 3 hr on a boiling water-bath with 50% sulphuric acid (20 ml), then allowed to cool and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was treated with sodium hydroxide solution till alkaline and then extracted with ether. The dried (MgSO₄) ether solution was evaporated to give the *title compounds* in ca. 50% yield which were crystallised from a suitable solvent (Table 2). The diazonium salts of (22) and (23) gave on coupling with β -naphthol reddish brown and brown azo-dyes, respectively.

4 (or 5)-Aroyl-1,5 (or 1,4)-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (27-31): (i) A solution of aroylphenylacetylene (24-26) (0.02 mol) and phenyl azide (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (20 ml) was refluxed for 24 hr. The solid precipitated on cooling to room temperature was filtered off and crystallised from ethanol to give 4-aryol-1,5-diphenyl isomers (27-29). The mother liquor from (28) and (29) contained the corresponding 5-aryol-1,4-diphenyl isomers (30 and 31, respectively) (Table 3).

(ii) Compounds (28) and (29) were also obtained by treating the stirred solution of the acid chloride (32) [prepared by refluxing the acid (1b) (2.65 g) with thionyl chloride (4 ml) for 2 hr and removing the excess of thionyl chloride by evaporation with light petroleum (b.p. 40°-60°) and dry benzene several times leaving a solid, m.p. 75° (2.7 g)] in chlorobenzene (30 ml) or in anisole (30 ml) with aluminium chloride (4.3 g) during 15 min. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 15 min, left overnight, then poured into ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the excess of solvent steam distilled. The residue was crystallised from ethanol to give (28) (3.3 g) m.p. 168°-70°, and (29) (3.4 g), m.p. 196°, undepressed on admixture with the products obtained by method (i).

Reaction of Aroylphenylacetylene with Hydrazines: Hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine (1 ml) was added dropwise with occasional shaking to a solution

of aroylphenylacetylene (24-26) (0.005 mol) in ethanol (15 ml.). The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 24 hr, and the precipitated products (quantitative yield) were crystallised from suitable solvents (Table 4).

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